

LEVERAGING TECHNOLOGY TO ENHANCE INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN MULTINATIONAL CORPORATIONS: A STRATEGIC APPROACH FOR GLOBAL KEY ACCOUNT MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Globalization has significantly reshaped the economic landscape, presenting both opportunities and challenges for multinational corporations (MNCs). Effective Global Key Account Management (GKAM) necessitates strong relationships with clients from diverse cultural backgrounds, making intercultural competence crucial. This study explores how technology can enhance intercultural competence in GKAM. By leveraging Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems, communication platforms, and data analytics, MNCs can better understand and manage cultural differences. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative interviews and case studies with quantitative surveys, to investigate the effectiveness of these technological tools. Findings indicate that CRM systems are highly effective in managing cultural data, communication platforms facilitate real-time intercultural interactions, and data analytics provide valuable insights into client behaviours and market trends. This integration of technology with intercultural competence not only improves client relationships but also enhances strategic decision-making, providing a significant competitive advantage for MNCs.

Keywords: Global Key Account Management (GKAM), Intercultural Competence, Multinational Corporations (MNCs), Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Communication Platforms, Data Analytics, Cultural Diversity, Technology Integration.

1. Introduction

Globalisation has profoundly altered the worldwide economic environment by presenting both prospects and obstacles for multinational corporations (MNCs). As businesses expand beyond their domestic borders, they encounter diverse cultural environments that require nuanced understanding and management. Globalisation has intensified competition, broadened markets and necessitated the integration of different cultural practices into business strategies. Managing global key accounts is essential in this situation, as these accounts frequently contribute significant amounts of an MNC's revenue and strategic positioning.

Intercultural competence which refers to the capacity to communicate and collaborate effectively in multiple cultural environments is now widely acknowledged as crucial for the success of Global Key Account Management (GKAM). Successful Global Key Account Management (GKAM) requires the establishment and upkeep of strong connections with clients from many cultural backgrounds. Intercultural competency empowers managers to effectively handle cultural disparities, minimise misinterpretations, cultivate trust, and promote collaboration. Consequently, it improves the overall efficiency of GKAM by aligning business strategies with the cultural demands and preferences of international customers.

Despite the acknowledged importance of intercultural competence, integrating it into GKAM practices presents significant challenges. Multinational corporations often struggle with the systematic incorporation of cultural awareness and sensitivity into their global strategies. This gap can lead to miscommunications, strategic misalignments and ultimately the erosion of key client relationships. The complexity of cultural dynamics adds an additional layer of difficulty. Requiring tailored approaches that can adapt to the specific cultural contexts of each client.

Technology offers a promising solution to these challenges by enhancing intercultural competence through various tools and systems. Technological advancements such as Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems, communication platforms and data analytics can support the integration of cultural insights into GKAM practices. These technologies can facilitate better understanding of client cultures, improve communication and enable the adaptation of strategies to meet the cultural expectations of key accounts. However, the potential of technology to enhance intercultural competence in GKAM has not been fully explored or utilized by many MNCs.

The main aim of this study is to investigate how technology may be utilised to improve intercultural competency in Global Key Account Management. The objective of this study is to examine how technological tools can be used to include intercultural competency into GKAM procedures. Moreover, it aims to create efficient technical solutions that might assist multinational organisations in effectively managing cultural diversity inside its main accounts. This study aims to create a strategic framework for implementing technology-enhanced intercultural competency in GKAM.

The structure of this study is intentionally crafted to methodically tackle the research objectives. The text commences with a thorough examination of the existing body of knowledge on intercultural competency, GKAM, and the impact of technology on global business practices. The methodology section provides a comprehensive overview of the mixed-methods approach employed in the study, including a detailed explanation of the data collecting and analysis methodologies. The findings section provides an overview of the outcomes derived from both qualitative and quantitative data, emphasising significant patterns and connections. Subsequently, there is an analysis that analyses the results within the framework of current literature

and practical ramifications. The paper provides advice for multinational organisations on how to use technology to improve intercultural competence in GKAM. It also suggests areas for future research.

2. Literature review

2.1. Intercultural competence

Intercultural competence is defined as the ability to interact effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations based on specific attitudes, intercultural knowledge, skills, and reflection. It is a multidimensional construct that encompasses cognitive, affective, and behavioural aspects. Enabling individuals to navigate and adapt to diverse cultural contexts [1-2] Theoretical frameworks such as Hofstede's [3-5] cultural dimensions theory, Hall's [6] context communication theory, and Trompenaars' [7] cultural dimensions provide a foundational understanding of how cultural differences manifest and influence interactions within multinational settings.

Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory is one of the most widely recognized frameworks in the study of intercultural competence. Hofstede identified six dimensions of culture: power distance, individualism versus collectivism, masculinity versus femininity, uncertainty avoidance, long-term versus short-term orientation, and indulgence versus restraint. These dimensions help to explain the variability in cultural norms and behaviours, providing a systematic way to compare and contrast different cultures. For instance, high power distance cultures tend to accept hierarchical order without much question, whereas low power distance cultures strive for equality and question authority [3-5]

Hall's high-context and low-context communication theory further contributes to the understanding of intercultural interactions. In high-context cultures, communication relies heavily on implicit messages and contextual elements such as body language and social status, whereas low-context cultures depend on explicit verbal communication. This distinction is crucial for global key account managers who must adapt their communication strategies to align with their clients' cultural communication preferences [6].

Trompenaars and Hampden-Turner's seven dimensions of culture, which include universalism versus particularism, individualism versus communitarianism, specific versus diffuse, neutral versus emotional, achievement versus ascription, sequential time versus synchronous time, and internal versus external control, offer additional insights into how cultural differences shape organizational behaviors and practices. Understanding these dimensions helps managers in multinational corporations develop culturally appropriate strategies for managing key accounts [7].

D. Panayotov and K. Hadzhiev [8-11] emphasize the importance of intercultural competence in managing global teams and customer relationships, highlighting the need for continuous cultural training and adaptation. Their research underscores that cultural awareness and sensitivity are critical for building trust and fostering collaboration in multinational environment.

2.2. Global Key Account Management

Global Key Account Management (GKAM) is a strategic approach focused on building and maintaining

long-term relationships with a company's most important global clients. The objective of GKAM is to foster close and collaborative partnerships that deliver mutual value over time. Effective GKAM requires a deep understanding of the client's business, markets, and cultural context. Which in turn necessitates high levels of intercultural competence among managers [12]

The strategic importance of GKAM lies in its potential to drive significant business growth and competitive advantage. According to Homburg, Workman, and Jensen [13], global key accounts often represent a substantial portion of a company's revenue and influence its strategic direction. As such, the ability to manage these accounts effectively is critical for multinational corporations. This involves not only meeting the immediate needs of key clients but also anticipating future needs and aligning them with the company's strategic goals.

One of the primary challenges in GKAM is navigating the cultural complexities that arise from managing accounts across different countries and regions. Misunderstandings and miscommunications stemming from cultural differences can hinder relationship building and negatively impact business outcomes. Therefore, integrating intercultural competence into GKAM practices is essential for fostering strong trust-based relationships with global clients.

2.3. The role of technology in multinational corporations

Technology plays a pivotal role in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of business operations in multinational corporations. Technological tools such as Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems, communication platforms, and data analytics have the potential to significantly improve GKAM by facilitating better understanding and management of cultural differences [14]

For instance, CRM systems enable companies to collect, store, and analyse data about their clients. Including cultural preferences and behaviours. This information can be used to tailor communication and strategies to align with the cultural context of key accounts. Furthermore, advanced CRM systems can integrate artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning algorithms to provide predictive insights and automate routine tasks. Allowing key account managers to focus on building relationships and strategic planning [15]

Communication platforms such as video conferencing tools and collaboration software help bridge the geographical and cultural distances between multinational teams and their clients. These technologies support real-time communication and collaboration, which are essential for managing global accounts. They also offer features such as language translation and cultural training modules that can enhance intercultural competence among managers [16-18]

Data analytics tools provide valuable insights into market trends, client behaviors, and performance metrics. By analyzing large datasets, companies can identify patterns and trends that inform strategic decisions and improve the management of global key accounts. Data-driven approaches enable more accurate and

timely responses to client needs, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of GKAM [19]

2.4. Integrating intercultural competence with technology in GKAM

The integration of intercultural competence with technological tools in GKAM represents a strategic opportunity for multinational corporations. By leveraging technology to enhance cultural understanding and communication. Companies can improve their ability to manage global key accounts effectively. This integration involves the use of CRM systems to collect and analyze cultural data, communication platforms to facilitate intercultural interactions and data analytics to inform strategic decisions.

Several studies have highlighted the benefits of combining intercultural competence with technology in global business practices. For example, a study by Stahl, Maznevski, Voigt, and Jonsen [16] found that culturally diverse teams that effectively use communication technologies are more innovative and perform better than homogeneous teams. Similarly, a survey conducted by the Boston Consulting Group revealed that companies with high intercultural competence and advanced technological capabilities are more likely to achieve their strategic goals in global markets.

Despite these benefits, many multinational corporations have yet to fully exploit the potential of technology-enhanced intercultural competence. Challenges such as resistance to change, lack of training and insufficient investment in technology can hinder the successful implementation of these strategies. Therefore, it is essential for companies to develop comprehensive frameworks and training programs that promote the integration of intercultural competence with technological tools.

3. Methods

3.1. Research Design

The research herein is a mixed-method study and adopts both the qualitative and quantitative techniques of research to comprehensively analyse how technology can enhance intercultural competence in GKAM. By integrating qualitative and quantitative data, a richer understanding of the subject can be obtained.

The qualitative component covers semi-structured interviews and case studies. Interviews were held with key account managers and executives of various multinational corporations to study the experience, challenges, and success of applying technology in intercultural competence development. Other case studies are also presented to evidence specific successful use of technology in intercultural competence development. A thematic analysis is done on qualitative data generated from the interviews and case studies. It works through the determination, examination, and presentation of patterns in the data. A software helped me organize and code data systematically to identify significant themes. The interview questions were open-ended, contained in a semi-structured interview guide, and specific to the impact of technology on intercultural competencies in GKAM.

Purposive sampling was used to select participants who had experience and knowledge regarding GKAM.

This test obtained clearance from the departmental review board and informed consent from the survey respondents before proceeding with data collection. The researcher followed ethical guidelines hence the rights and well-being of the participants in the study were protected.

To conduct the quantitative part, the test issued surveys to a larger sample size - key account managers and executives across different industries. The survey supplied some questions concerning the effectiveness of specific technological tools to enhance intercultural competence. The responses were utilized to measure their perception regarding the impact that such tools would have on GKAM practices. Some statistical techniques were used for quantitative data coming from the surveys. The descriptive statistics summarized the data, consisting of frequencies, means, and standard deviations. Inference from inferential statistics, such as the correlation and regression analysis, was an involvement of the use of technological tools to enhance intercultural competencies.

The survey questionnaire consists of open-ended and closed questions coupled with Likert-scale questions, capturing dimensions that can measure perceptions of the effectiveness of these tools. The survey also captured demographic information and organizational context to control for potential confounding variables. More importantly, a stratified random sampling method was applied to ensure representation across various industries and company sizes. Therefore, it allowed generalizability of the topic.

4. Results

4.1. Qualitative findings

The qualitative data from interviews and case studies provided rich insights into how technology enhances intercultural competence in Global Key Account Management (GKAM). Several key themes emerged.

First, many managers reported on the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems to collect and analyze cultural information. CRM empowers the manager to design how they communicate in line with the culture of their customers. For example, managers would use information extracted from CRM to understand, for instance, cultural subtleties within negotiation styles and decision-making processes. Consequently, interaction with critical accounts became more effective and personalized.

This was followed by communication platforms that bridged both geographical and cultural differences through the use of video conferencing tools and collaboration software. This facilitated real-time communication and collaboration to support the management of globally dispersed teams and clients. The others, such as real-time translation and cultural training modules, also became perfect for helping the managers manoeuvre through cultural differences.

Lastly, data analytics tools were found valuable for providing insights about the behaviours of clients and the trends in the market. Managers could decipher patterns in large datasets to arrive at strategic decisions. This data-driven approach opened opportunities for

managers to better and more accurately respond to client needs more promptly, thereby improving the effectiveness of GKAM.

4.2. Quantitative findings

Results of the quantitative survey validated these results and also elaborated on how effective technological tools are in improving intercultural competence.

Most of the respondents stated that they found CRM systems effectively to handle cultural information. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 5 is the highest stage of effectiveness, the average mark of CRM systems came out to be equal to 4.2. Most respondents noted that CRM systems had allowed them to learn and, to a greater extent, had allowed them to satisfy the cultural needs of their key accounts.

Communication platforms received high scores for effectiveness as well. Video conferencing tools were rated an average of 4.1, while collaboration software was rated at 4.0. Respondents emphasized that these tools assisted them in ensuring the consistency and clarity of communication with clients from various cultural backgrounds.

Data analytics tools were rated slightly lower, with an average effectiveness rating of 3.8. While still considered valuable, some respondents noted challenges in integrating these tools into their existing GKAM processes. The ones using data analytics tools effectively reported a significant enhancement in their capability to predict and meet client requirements satisfactorily.

It was found from the analysis that there was a significant positive relationship between the use of CRM systems and improved client relationships ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$). The use of communication platforms also positively correlated with better intercultural issues understanding during global accounts management ($r = 0.60$, $p < 0.01$). Data analytic tools were also positively related to GKAM with enhanced outcomes, but at a slightly lower strength of 0.55 at $p < 0.05$.

Correlation analysis showed a strong positive relationship between the use of CRM systems and improved client relationships ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, the use of communication platforms was positively correlated with better intercultural understanding ($r = 0.60$, $p < 0.01$). The relationship between data analytics tools and enhanced GKAM outcomes was also positive, though slightly weaker ($r = 0.55$, $p < 0.05$).

4.3. Combined insights

The qualitative and quantitative findings both show that technology plays an imperative role in enhancing intercultural competence for GKAM. CRM systems, communication platforms, and data analytics tools—all bring something unique to this purpose. Of the three, CRM systems are very effective in managing cultural data, while communication platforms and data analytics bridge the culture gap through insights. Hence, managers who integrated these technologies into their GKAM practices did indeed report better relationships with their clients, improved cultural understanding, and better strategic decision-making. These findings suggest that investments in such technological tools, accompanied by training for managers, will ena-

ble a significant advantage for multinational corporations while operating in the complexities of global key account management.

5. Discussion

5.1. Interpretation of findings

The results of this research will help provide a complete overview of the role of technology in developing intercultural competence in GKAM. The analysis revealed several critical ways in which technological tools contribute to better management of global key accounts.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Systems

CRM systems emerged as a highly effective tool for managing cultural data. The qualitative data highlighted that CRM systems enable the storage and retrieval of information about clients' cultural backgrounds, preferences, and behaviours at a granular level. This aspect may assist managers in better aligning their communication strategies and business approaches with the culture-based expectations of the client. For instance, one respondent mentioned that he used the data from the CRM to understand some of the specific cultural norms associated with conducting business meetings, which proved very useful in organizing and conducting such meetings. The survey therefore talks of the significance of the CRM systems by their high effectiveness rating. According to the managers, this system assists them to develop a more personalized relationship with clients. Managers reported that these systems help them build stronger, more personalized relationships with clients, which is essential for trust and long-term collaboration.

The CRM helps in better coordination within teams since the information regarding clients is stored in a centralized database. This means that all members of the team are informed of the cultural considerations and can maintain uniformity in their interaction with clients. Providing managers with historical data related to client interaction also allows them to track the developments achieved, recognize patterns, and more accurately predict what their clients are likely to require.

Communication Platforms

Video conferencing and collaboration software have helped bridge geographical and cultural distances between employees. Since it provides real-time communication at different time zones and in other geographic locations, the tool's usefulness was rated relatively high—the video conferencing tool was rated at 4.1, and collaboration software was rated 4.0 on a 5-point scale. These platforms facilitate real-time communication, which is essential for maintaining relationships with clients across different time zones and regions.

More important is the added value that a communication platform offers by providing support for visual and verbal cues that must be present in intercultural communication. Other features, such as instant translation and cultural training modules, help managers navigate language barriers and cultural differences. These tools, according to the qualitative data, reduce misunderstandings and improve the process of cross-cultural meetings. For example, a manager from a multinational

corporation highlighted how video conferencing tools enabled more nuanced communication through visual aids and face-to-face interaction. Which are often lacking in email or phone communication.

Additionally, the collaboration software also allows for shared workspaces for team members hailing from diverse cultures to enable real-time collaboration on a project. This makes an environment more inclusive, providing cultural perspectives in the decision-making processes. An integral part of this is the capability to share documents, monitor changes, and manage tasks collectively, along with new abilities to do work and projects effectively.

Data Analytics Tools

Data analytics tools, while rated slightly lower in effectiveness (3.8 on a 5-point scale), play a crucial role in providing insights into client behaviours and market trends. These tools enable managers to analyse large datasets to identify patterns and trends that inform strategic decisions. The ability to process and interpret complex data allows managers to anticipate client needs and respond proactively.

It was expressed qualitatively in the results, where managers who use data analytics very well can point out some critical cultural factors affecting client decisions. For instance, from the pattern of purchases and feedback, he can change the offerings in a manner that reflects the cultural orientation of the clients. In addition, they said that the use of data analytics has indeed placed them in a better position to understand seasonal trends and cultural events that influence buying behaviour, thus being able to devise more focused marketing strategies.

However, the survey also highlighted some challenges in incorporating data analytics tools into the conventional GKAM processes. Most important in this respect is the acquisition of the specialized skills necessary for correctly interpreting data and the initial investments that need to be made toward setting these systems up. However, the positive correlation between the usage of data analytics and better GKAM results ($r = 0.55$, $p < 0.05$) does show the importance of these tools for strategic planning and decision-making.

5.2. Practical implications

Some practical implications of the findings of this research for the multinational corporations interested in achieving intercultural competence while doing Global Key Account Management are as follows: with technological tools like CRM systems, communication platforms, and data analytics effectively integrated, a company will reach a high level of cultural difference management in building strong client relationships.

Multinational companies should invest in high-tech CRM systems capable of capturing and analyzing cultural data. Such systems should be able to collect vast amounts of information about cultural backgrounds, preferences, modes of communication, and processes used in making decisions by the clients. It's in this way that the companies would align their strategies for engaging with the cultural expectations of their clients. For example, a CRM system tracking cultural preferences may alert management to the necessity of changing communication styles when interacting with

customers from a high-context culture, one in which non-verbal and implicit communication channels are predominant.

Comprehensive training and development programs for key account managers will enable the company to extract maximum value out of technological tools. These programs are responsible for not only the technical skills to be gained in utilizing CRM systems, communication platforms, and analytics tools but also for intercultural competence. The training has to include such modules as cultural awareness, sensitivity, and effective means of communication in various cultural contexts. Making managers better at understanding culture and more technologically knowledgeable ensures that a company's teams are better prepared for the competent management of global key accounts.

This work between different countries and cultures requires communication platforms using video conferencing tools and collaborating software. With these platforms, real-time communication and collaboration can occur between teams in disparate geographical locations and the clients. Some features that go a long way in increasing a manager's capability of working around cultural differences include instant translation services, cultural training modules and virtual meeting capabilities. For example, video conferencing tools with translation features might be used to make the managers better communicate with their clients who speak other languages and reduce the likelihood of misunderstanding. Data analytics tools can be used to gain insights into client behaviours, market trends, and cultural patterns.

Data analytics tools should be employed to gain insights into client behaviours, market trends, and cultural patterns. By analysing large datasets, companies can identify trends and patterns that inform strategic decisions. For example, data analytics can reveal cultural preferences in purchasing behaviours, allowing companies to tailor their marketing strategies to different cultural segments. Predictive analytics can also help managers anticipate client needs and proactively address potential issues, leading to higher client satisfaction and stronger relationships.

Organizations should foster a culture of continuous learning and adaptation. As technology evolves, staying updated with the latest tools and techniques will be crucial for maintaining a competitive advantage. Companies should encourage their managers to participate in ongoing training and development programs, attend industry conferences, and engage in knowledge-sharing activities. By staying informed about the latest technological advancements and best practices, managers can continuously improve their intercultural competence and GKAM strategies.

Based on the insights gained from this study, multinational corporations should develop strategic frameworks that integrate technology with intercultural competence. These frameworks should outline clear guidelines for using CRM systems, communication platforms, and data analytics to manage global key accounts. For example, a strategic framework might include protocols for capturing cultural data in CRM systems, best practices for conducting virtual meetings

with international clients, and methods for analysing cultural trends using data analytics. By providing a structured approach, companies can ensure consistent and effective implementation across their global operations.

5.3. Theoretical Contributions

This study makes several significant contributions to the existing body of literature on intercultural competence and its integration with technology in Global Key Account Management (GKAM).

Firstly, the research provides empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of CRM systems in enhancing intercultural competence. Previous studies have primarily focused on the theoretical aspects of intercultural competence [3-7], but this study bridges the gap between theory and practice by demonstrating how CRM systems can be used to capture and analyze cultural data. This practical application enriches our understanding of how technological tools can operationalize theoretical concepts of intercultural competence in real-world business settings.

Secondly, the study extends the theoretical framework of intercultural communication by examining the role of advanced communication platforms. The integration of features such as instant translation and cultural training modules into these platforms provides a new dimension to Hall's [6] high-context and low-context communication theory. By facilitating real-time, culturally informed interactions, these tools enhance the applicability of intercultural communication theories in the context of global business operations.

Thirdly, the research contributes to the understanding of data-driven decision-making in the realm of intercultural competence. While existing literature has highlighted the importance of data analytics in business strategy [19], this study specifically examines its impact on GKAM. The findings demonstrate that data analytics tools not only provide insights into client behaviours and market trends but also help managers anticipate and address cultural nuances. This expands the theoretical discussion on how data analytics can be integrated with intercultural competence frameworks to enhance strategic decision-making.

Furthermore, the study's mixed-methods approach offers a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between technology and intercultural competence. By combining qualitative insights with quantitative data, the research provides a holistic view of how different technological tools contribute to managing cultural differences in GKAM.

Lastly, the research identifies practical implications that are directly applicable to the development of training programs and strategic frameworks for multinational corporations. By demonstrating the tangible benefits of integrating CRM systems, communication platforms, and data analytics into GKAM, the study provides actionable insights that can be incorporated into managerial practices. This practical application of theoretical concepts enhances the relevance and utility of intercultural competence theories in the field of global business management.

Overall, this study contributes to the theoretical discourse by providing empirical evidence and practical applications of intercultural competence in the context of technology enhanced GKAM. It bridges the gap between theory and practice, extends existing frameworks, and offers new insights into the role of technological tools in managing cultural differences. These contributions enrich the academic understanding of intercultural competence and provide valuable guidance for practitioners aiming to navigate the complexities of global key account management.

5.4. Limitations and future research

This study has several limitations. Qualitative data from purposive sampling could lead to biases because the participants with specific experiences were overrepresented, limiting the variety of perspectives. Besides, the qualitative data may not be entirely generalizable to all multinational corporations due to organizational differences in context and culture.

The survey's reliance on self-reported data can also lead to bias as respondents may provide socially desirable answers or may not accurately recall their experiences with technological tools. This self-reporting bias can affect the validity of the findings. Moreover, the cross-sectional design of the study which captures data at a single point in time limits the ability to infer causality between the use of technology and the enhancement of intercultural competence. Longitudinal studies would be needed to establish causal relationships more definitively.

Another limitation is that it potentially involves different kinds of technological tools among companies and industries, thus influencing the results encountered. Besides, it assumes a level of technological know-how on the part of the respondent, which might not be uniform across the sample.

Future research should consider longitudinal studies to establish causal relationships more definitively. Specific technological tools in various cultural and organizational contexts merit more detailed investigations. Subsequent studies might explore the impact of such new technologies as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) on intercultural competence and GKAM.

6. Conclusion

This study investigated the role of technology in enhancing intercultural competence within Global Key Account Management (GKAM). By combining qualitative and quantitative methods, a comprehensive understanding of how CRM systems, communication platforms and data analytics can improve GKAM practices.

The findings underscore the importance of CRM systems in managing cultural information. These systems allow managers to tailor communication strategies to the cultural preferences of their clients. This leads to more personalized and effective interactions. The high effectiveness ratings for CRM systems highlight their critical role in building and maintaining strong client relationships.

Communication platforms, such as video conferencing tools and collaboration software, are essential for bridging geographical and cultural gaps. These tools

facilitate real-time communication and collaboration, enhancing the ability of managers to navigate cultural differences. The features of these platforms, including instant translation and cultural training modules, were particularly valued by the respondents.

Data analytics tools provide valuable insights into client behaviors and market trends. By analyzing large datasets managers can identify patterns that inform strategic decisions. This data-driven approach allows managers to anticipate and meet client needs more effectively. Although data analytics tools were rated slightly lower than CRM systems and communication platforms, their positive impact on GKAM practices is evident.

The study's mixed-methods approach revealed that combining these technological tools enhances intercultural competence in GKAM. Managers who effectively integrate these technologies report better client relationships, improved cultural understanding and enhanced strategic decision-making. These findings suggest that multinational corporations can significantly benefit from investing in and training their managers to use these technologies.

Theoretical contributions of this study include empirical support for the practical application of intercultural competence frameworks and extending these frameworks to include technological tools. The integration of cultural data into CRM systems, real-time intercultural interactions through communication platforms and data-driven decision-making enhance the theoretical understanding of intercultural competence in global business.

Practically, the research provides actionable insights for multinational corporations. Investing in advanced CRM systems, sophisticated communication platforms, and robust data analytics tools can provide a strategic advantage in managing global key accounts. Training programs should focus on both the technical and cultural aspects of these tools to maximize their effectiveness.

This research has limitations, including potential bias in qualitative sampling and reliance on self-reported data. The cross-sectional design also limits the ability to infer causality. Future research should consider longitudinal studies to establish causal relationships and explore specific technological tools in more detail.

In conclusion, leveraging technology to enhance intercultural competence in GKAM is both feasible and beneficial. By integrating CRM systems, communication platforms, and data analytics into GKAM practices, multinational corporations can improve their global key account management. Leading to better business outcomes and stronger global partnerships. These insights provide a valuable roadmap for both practitioners and researchers in the field of global business management.

Conflicts of interest

The author declares no competing interests that could influence the content of this paper.

Consent to participate

Informed consent was secured from all individual participants who took part in the study.

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